

OIL PIPELINE VANDALISATION AND THE ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFECTS ON RURAL COMMUNITIES.

Tonbra R. ODUBO 1 and Ajoke M. OMOLADE 2

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author's Contact: tonbraodubo@ndu.edu.ng +2347066115919

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15814324>

Abstract

The commercial exploration of crude oil in Nigeria, spurred the massive construction of network of pipelines. Incidentally, the cases of oil pipeline vandalism have been on the increase in the country. Unfortunately, oil pipeline vandalism is a major source of oil pollution, leading to environmental degradation and loss of revenue to the nation. The study considered oil pipeline vandalisation and the environmental and socio-economic effects on rural communities. The area of study is Okolobiri community, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey research design was used for the study. With a sample size of 390, the data were sourced through primary and secondary sources. Using descriptive statistics, the study revealed the environmental and socio-economic impact of oil pipeline vandalism, leading to the destruction of traditional means of livelihoods. It was established that pipeline vandalism causes massive oil pollution. It was thus recommended that there should be increased surveillance of pipelines as well as stricter penalties and enforcement of the law by the government against pipeline vandalism. The local communities should, through awareness programmes and job creation initiatives, be sensitized and engaged to avoid involvement in pipeline vandalism. Also, the government and operating oil companies should instal remote-controlled shut-off valves to protect valve heads from destruction. There is also the need for increased collaboration between oil companies, government agencies, and local communities through a multifaceted approach to mitigate pipeline vandalism. Government should also ensure the provision of infrastructure and increased affordability of petroleum products to make oil pipeline interdiction unattractive.

Key Words: Environment, Oil Pipeline, Socio-Economic, Rural Communities, Vandalism

Introduction

Oil pipelines are common features in Nigeria, following the presence of crude oil as a natural resource. Pipelines are laid to crisscross vast areas of land and water laying for crude oil transportation. The commercial exploration of crude oil in Nigeria, which attracted unprecedented revenue, spurred the massive construction of network of pipelines for massive crude oil distribution. This commercial exploration was expanded to all parts of Nigeria for massive distribution and redistribution of oil. The expansion also increases the risk of disasters caused by various factors, among which, are lack of adequate evaluation by environmental protection agencies and the poor concern for environmental threats by the populace (Olawuni, et al 2020). According to the petroleum industry act (2021), oil pipeline means every part of any tubular infrastructure by which means petroleum (liquid or gas) is conveyed. Oil production in Nigeria, which is the corner stone of the Nigerian economy was first extracted in 1956. The exploration and production commenced in 1956 at Oloibiri, in current Bayelsa State, Nigeria. So far, oil production had been on the increase. It has been asserted that from the sixties till date, much revenue had been realized by the Nigerian government. An estimated revenue of US \$600million was made by the country (Okoli, 2013). The country earns lots of revenue from oil yearly. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) report (2024) posits that N1.116 trillion was recorded from oil in December, 2024 alone. The increase revenue spurred the massive construction of pipelines. Pipes were laid to crisscross vast areas of land and water for crude oil transportation, occasioning higher risks for disaster due to problems of environmental protection agencies limitations and human interference due to limited concern for disaster by most of the populace (Olawuni et al, 2020). This led to the creation of buffer zones under the petroleum Act of 1965, which is now statutorily protected under the rights of way for Petroleum Product Pipelines in Nigeria. The pipeline Act of 1965 played a major role in

ensuring the simplification of the procedures and the determination of the condition under which pipelines are constructed in Nigeria. Arising from this, a major problem arose. The issue of pipeline vandalism has become a regular occurrence, particularly in contemporary Nigeria. Solomon and Madubuike, (2011), states that oil pipeline vandalisation is “the illegal or unauthorised act of destroying or puncturing of oil pipelines so as to disrupt supply or to siphon crude oil or its refined products for purposes of appropriating it for personal use or for sale on the black market or any other outlet.” This process involves stealing crude oil direct from the well head, using hose to fill tankers. These oil products are taken to illegal refineries, refined and sold domestically or at international markets (Sloan and Schmitz, 2019).

NNPC (2016), records 14,607 cases of oil pipeline vandalism in the Niger Delta from 2003 to 2015 and a loss of 10.9 billion US Dollars from 2009 to 2011 (NEITI, 2013).

These numerous cases cause oil spills and pollution, which lead to loss of farmlands, poverty, migration, etc. The spills have socio-economic, environmental, and humanitarian consequences (Onuoha, 2009). Despite the economic growth and development that accrue to African nations through oil exploitation, the oil-producing areas suffer from severe environmental degradation. A typical example is the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. These effects and neglect of the environment due to mismanagement drives pipeline disasters such as vandalism (Johnson, et al, 2022).

The Nigerian government, using various security agencies, has adopted various methods to curb the menace of oil pipeline vandalism (Nwoke et al, 2022). Oluwatuyi and Ileri, (2013) thus remarked that efforts to curbing pipeline vandalism is a complex issue that requires multi-faceted solutions, including addressing poverty and unemployment, improving local infrastructure, and

promoting alternative livelihoods for affected communities. It remains a challenge for the Nigerian government to effectively tackle pipeline vandalism and its associated problems.

Literature Review

Vandalism constitutes willful destruction of property. Within the context of governance, it is the willful destruction of government property (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). In Nigeria, the motivation is to steal oil products for material gains. The perpetrators of this act, drill into pipelines to intentionally steal the oil.

Oil pipeline vandalism has been escalating in Nigeria (Odalonu, 2015). This has affected sustainable governance in its oil and gas industry (Nwoke et al, 2022).

A major source of pipeline vandalism is the reaction to environmental degradation and neglect by community members. The environmental destruction of the Niger Delta has caused economic depravity due to the disruption of farming and fishing activities. Damage on water bodies, farmlands has reduced economic activities. The region has suffered severe damage to its biodiversity generally, leading to the pollution of air, water and land, causing health problems and food shortages (Igbani, et al. 2024). All these have resulted in oil pipelines vandalism by community members in order to scoop oil for sale for economic survival (Njoku, 2016). Thus, poverty is a major driver of pipeline vandalism in Nigeria. There is a nexus between increase in crude oil refining by locals and worsening economic conditions in the country (Ozogu et al, 2023).

Illegal crude oil refining is a major factor that has encouraged oil pipeline vandalism. Though the refineries have some economic advantage to the operators, they contribute significantly to the destruction of the environment through air, land and water pollution, leading to negative effects on wildlife, water and the vegetation. The refineries are mostly operated in the creeks of the

Niger Delta region. Operators and other culprits burst oil pipelines that convey oil to various locations, tap the crude oil and move same to oil tanks for refining (Adishi & Hunga, 2017).

Nnadih and Offiong (2017), asserts that pipeline vandalism in the Niger Delta is linked to resource control struggles by militants who emerged to oppose the existing order of perceived injustices by the government and the oil companies on the people of the region.

Another source of pipeline vandalism is corruption. According to Bodo et al (2020), corruption within the oil sector drives pipeline vandalism. He explained that there is an affiliation between the vandals and NNPC personnels. He said some NNPC personnels usually contact the perpetrators of this heinous crime whenever products were being discharged into the pipelines. He described Lagos and Ogun states as hot beds of fuel theft. Oil pipeline vandalism and oil theft activities are causing the environment and the Nigerian economy to decline by the day. In some cases, some individuals illegally construct oil pipelines to divert crude oil and refined products to desired destinations without the intervention of the government (Henry & Mohammed, 2023) .

Youth Unemployment is also a source of pipeline vandalism. The rise of youth unemployment has prompted pipeline vandalism as a means of survival (Johnson, et al, 2022). Corrosion is also a major factor for pipeline vandalization, followed by sabotage, induced by poverty and unemployment (Johnson, et al, 2022). Lack of community-based security to secure pipelines expose them to pipeline vandalism. Inadequate maintenance of pipes and other essential parts also creates vulnerability, leading to vandalism and even explosion in Nigeria (Johnson, et al, 2022).

An international cartel on pipeline vandalism, oil theft and oil bunkering exist. This has created complicated network of pipeline vandals and oil thieves whose primary motive is to scoop crude oil for sale (Bodo et al 2020).

The effects of pipeline vandalism are quite numerous. Pipeline vandalism affects the power sector of the country (Nwoke et al, 2022). The vandalisation of oil pipelines can thus, plunge several parts of the country in darkness due to shortage of several megawatts (Njoku, 2016). This scenario creates low productivity due to the cost of using private power plants for production. Also, pipeline vandalism is a source of social insecurity. For example, operating oil companies are sometimes, compelled to stop work or threatened by aggrieved community members. Also, the situation creates scarcity of petroleum products, increase in transport fare and prices of consumer goods and loss of Nigeria's national income (Njoku, 2016).

A major effect of pipeline is environmental degradation. The Niger Delta region has suffered enormous destruction to its environment and livelihood. The apparent pollution of air, water and land causes health problems and food shortages (Igbani, et al. 2024). Olawuni et al (2020), identified shortage of environmental protection agencies in the country and residents low concern for environmental threats as contributors to disaster. The activities involving vandalism and tapping crude oil from oil installations causes damage and leaks that leads to environmental degradation which leads to the destruction of farmlands and forests (Odalonu, 2015). Victims of environmental pollution hold discriminatory perceptions. Such perceptions on damage from environmental pollution shows that as environmental disasters are based on a specific environmental change, victims experienced discriminatory damage after the incident (Lee & Kim, 2021).

Theoretical framework

The theory used in the study is the “frustration-aggression theory (FAT)” propounded by John Dollard et al (1939). The theory portrays that people indulge in violent acts based on psychological factors that influence their behavioural pattern. The theory basically asks the questions, what do people feel and want? What are their expectations in terms of needs and satisfaction? Thus, a variance between satisfaction and needs will trigger frustration and confrontation with their perceived oppressors, those they claim to be responsible for their frustration (Okoli, 2013). This relates to the cause of oil pipelines vandalism in the Niger Delta. The expectations of the people were high on the issue of massive development of their communities by the Multinational Oil Companies (MNOCs), since the discovery of oil and natural gas in 1956.

Their expectations on infrastructural facilities such as electricity, roads, health care, employment, etc. as applicable in host communities in Europe, were dashed. They therefore, as a way of protest, started vandalising oil pipelines to express their frustration of neglect. The outcome of such action is a decline in national revenue, environmental degradation etc. This theory thus applies to the study area in the Niger Delta where the frustration caused by MNOCs and the federal government has led to protests and reactions leading to pipeline vandalism and artisanal crude oil refining. According to Gurr (1970) in his book “Why Men Rebel”, if what is sought is not attained after a prolonged wait period, and with an outlook of not attainable, the higher the possibility that anger and violence will prevail.

Materials and Methods

Area of Study

The area of study is Okolobiri, a community located in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa state, Nigeria. The community was founded by migrant settlers. These settlers were primarily farmers and fishermen who established their homesteads along the Nun River, which flows through the area. Over time, Okolobiri became an important trading hub due to its strategic location along the river. The community served as a major point of exchange for goods and commodities between the interior regions and the coastal areas of the Niger Delta.

The discovery of oil in commercial quantities in the Niger Delta region in the mid-20th century had a profound impact on Okolobiri. Oil extraction activities began in the area, bringing positive and negative effects. While the oil industry brought some opportunities, it also resulted in environmental degradation and socio-economic challenges for the community.

The study considered oil pipeline vandalism and the environmental and Socio-economic effects on rural communities. This study employed a cross-sectional survey research design. The sample size was 390, derived from a population of 16,083 with the use of Taro Yameni's formula. The sampling technique involves the purposive selection of three (3) compounds out of the compounds that make up the area of study. The simple random sampling technique was employed to select the respondents for the study. The study made use of secondary and primary data. The data analysis was based on descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentages.

Findings and Discussion

Socio-Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Table 1: Sex of Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Male	225	57.7
Female	165	42.3

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Male	225	57.7
Female	165	42.3
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis of the sex of the respondents in table 1 shows that 225(57.7%) are male while 165(42.3%) are female.

Table 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
18-25	88	22.6
26-40	138	35.4
41-60	104	26.7
61 years and above	60	15.3
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The age distribution in Table 2 shows that 88(22.6%) respondents are 18-25 years, 138(35.4%) are 26-30 years, 104(26.7%) are 31-35 years, while 60(15.3%) are 56 years and above.

Table 3: Occupation of Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Farming	73	18.7

Fishing	57	14.7
Trader	50	12.8
Civil servant	70	17.9
Student	65	16.7
Unemployed	30	7.7
Others	45	11.5
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

In terms of the occupation of the respondents, table 3 shows that 73(18.7%) are into farming; 57(14.7%) are into fishing; 50(12.8%) are traders; 70(17.9%) are civil servants; 65(16.7%) are students; 30(7.7%) are unemployed while 45(11.5%) do other jobs for a living.

Table 4: Oil pipeline vandalism as a significant problem in the community

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	248	63.6
No	142	36.4
Total	390	100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4 shows that 248(63.6%) respondents considered oil pipeline vandalism as a significant problem in their community, while 142(36.4%) did not.

Table 5: Poor socio-economic circumstances as a cause of oil pipeline vandalism

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	218	55.9
No	172	44.1
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 5 shows poor socio-economic circumstances as a cause of oil pipeline vandalism. From the table, 218(55.9%) respondents considered poor socio-economic circumstances as a cause of oil pipeline vandalism, while 172(44.1%) respondents did not consider it as such.

Table 6: Whether oil pipeline vandalism negatively affects the environment

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	248	63.6
No	142	36.4
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 6 shows whether oil pipeline vandalism negatively affects the environment. The result shows that 248(63.6%) respondents averred that oil pipeline vandalism negatively affects the environment, while 142(36.4%) said no.

Table 7: How oil pollution from pipeline vandalism affects livelihood

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Destruction of farmland and crops	176	45.1
Pollution of river water	120	30.8
Destruction of forest resources	94	24.1
Total	390	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 7 shows how oil pollution from pipeline vandalism affects respondent's livelihood. 176(45.1%) respondents affirmed that oil pollution from pipeline vandalism destroy farmland and crops, 120(30.8%) were of the view that oil pollution from pipeline vandalism

pollutes river water, while 94(24.1%) averred that oil pollution from pipeline vandalism destroy forest resources.

Discussion of Findings

The research findings underscored the prevalence of pipeline vandalism as a significant problem in the study area. The study revealed poor socio-economic circumstances of the community members as a major source of pipeline vandalism. This is attributable to the seeming neglect of oil-bearing communities in the Niger Delta region by the government and oil companies. Their expectations on infrastructural facilities such as electricity supply, road networks, health care delivery system, employment, etc. as applicable in host communities in Europe, were dashed. They therefore, as a way of protest, started vandalising oil pipelines to express their frustration over the long years of neglect. The finding is in line with the finding that despite the economic growth and development that accrues to African nations through oil exploitation, the oil producing areas suffer from severe environmental degradation resulting in the busting of oil pipelines by community members in order to scoop oil for sale for the purpose of economic survival (Njoku, 2016). A typical example is the Niger Delta region of Nigeria where pipelines are busted and the crude oil, conveyed to illegal refineries for refining or sold at the international market due to neglect by the government and other stakeholders. This neglect of the environment and humans by the government and operating oil companies due to mismanagement, drives pipeline disasters such as vandalism (Johnson, et al, 2022). The finding also corroborates the assertion that there is a nexus between increase in crude oil refining by locals and worsening economic conditions in the country (Ozogu et al, 2023).

The study also shows that a substantial proportion of the respondents perceived pipeline vandalism as a significant problem in their community, no matter the underlying socio-economic

circumstances that drives such actions. In discussing the findings on the environmental effects of oil pipeline vandalism, it is evident that a significant portion of respondents recognize the negative consequences associated with such activities. Specifically, most respondents agreed that oil pipeline vandalism has a detrimental effect on the environment and thus, harm wildlife and ecosystems. The findings align with the finding that activities involving vandalism and tapping crude oil from oil installations causes damage and leaks that leads to environmental degradation which leads to the destruction of farmlands and forests (Odalonu, 2015). Clearly, the paper addressed the fact that a significant portion of respondents recognize the negative consequences of pipeline vandalism on the environment.

The study also identified the socio-economic impact of oil pipeline vandalism and provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by communities affected by such activities. A notable proportion of respondents considered the broader implications of pipeline vandalism beyond environmental concerns. Most respondents reported observing evidence of decreased property values in areas where oil pipeline vandalism is prevalent. This observation underscores the detrimental effect of pipeline vandalism on local economies and property markets, potentially leading to financial losses for property owners and decreased investment attractiveness in affected in areas within the region. The study identified the diverse livelihoods of respondents in the study area, with significant proportion engaged in farming, fishing, hunting, and other activities. It revealed that a substantial number of respondents perceive oil pollution as adversely affecting their livelihoods, indicating the direct socio-economic impact of pipeline vandalism on community members ability to sustain themselves and generate income.

The study also identified various ways oil pollution affects livelihoods of the respondents. These includes the destruction of farmland and crops, pollution of river water, and depletion of forest

resources. These findings highlight the interconnectedness between environmental degradation caused by oil spills and the socio-economic well-being of individuals who are reliant on natural resources for their livelihoods. The findings are in line with the finding that activities involving vandalism and tapping of crude oil from oil installations causes damage and leaks that leads to environmental degradation which leads to the destruction of farmlands and forests (Odalonu, 2015). The findings also corroborate the claim that the numerous cases of pipeline vandalism, causes oil spills and environmental pollution (land, air, and water), which occasioned loss of farmlands, poverty, migration etc. because oil pipeline vandalism has a nexus with social, economic, environmental, and humanitarian consequences (Onuoha, 2009). Despite the adverse effects observed, there exist, the presence of a minority of respondents who do not feel as much impact of oil pipeline vandalism on their livelihoods, compared to others. And this suggests potential gaps in awareness or differing perspectives within the surveyed population. Certain livelihood activities were reported to be less affected by oil spillage compared to others. This variation underscores the resilience and adaptability of certain respondents in the face of environmental challenges, while also highlighting the differential impact of pipeline vandalism on diverse livelihoods within affected communities. The finding is supported by the empirical study of Lee and Kim (2021), that victims of environmental pollution hold discriminatory perceptions. They averred that perceptions on damage from environmental pollution shows that as environmental disasters are based on a specific environmental change, victims experienced discriminatory damage after the incident.

Conclusions

The research findings underscored the severity and persistence of pipeline vandalism in the study area due to factors such as poverty and poor socio-economic circumstances of the community

members. These circumstances were occasioned, primarily, by the neglect of oil-bearing communities in the Niger Delta region by the government and oil companies. The aftermath of pipeline vandalism is more environmental degradation which affects diverse livelihoods such as farming, fishing, hunting, and other activities. This direct socio-economic impact of pipeline vandalism on community members affects their ability to sustain themselves from the natural environment. The prevalence of oil pipeline vandalism is evidently a significant problem, which requires the need for mitigation through proactive measures.

Recommendations

- There is need for increased surveillance as well as stricter penalties and enforcement of the law by the government against pipeline vandalism.
- The local communities should, through awareness programmes and job creation initiatives, be sensitized and engaged to avoid involvement in pipeline vandalism.
- The government and operating oil companies should invest in technology and the installation of remote-controlled shut-off valves to protect valve heads from destruction.
- There is need for increased collaboration between oil companies, government agencies, and local communities through a multifaceted approach to mitigating pipeline vandalism, integrating both technological advancements and community engagement strategies.
- Petroleum products should be made available and affordable to discourage oil pipeline vandalism.
- Since the vandalisation of oil pipelines is an expression of frustration over neglect the government should provide electricity, roads, health care, employment, etc.

References

- Adishi, E., & Hunga, M.O., (2017). Oil Theft, Illegal Bunkering and Pipeline Vandalism: Its Impact on Nigeria's Economy, 2015-2016. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/3711281>
- Bodo, T. Gimah B.G., & Kemetony J., (2020). Illegal Oil Bunkering in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria: A Challenge to Nigeria's Development. *European Scientific Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2020.v16n29p134>
- Dollard, J., Miller, N. E., Doob, L. W., Mowrer, O. H., & Sears, R. R. (1939). Frustration and aggression. Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1037/10022-000>
- Henry, A., & Mohammed, S.U., (2023). Oil Pipelines Vandalism and Oil Theft: Security Threat to Nigerian Economy and Environment. *Journal of Environmental Law & Policy* | 03 (01). <https://doi.org/10.33002/jelp03.01.05>.
- Igbani, F., Ronald, W I A., & Weapngong, (2024) effects of illegal refineries on aquatic life in Niger delta: a review *international journal of environment and pollution research*. 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijepr.13/vol12n1117>
- Johnson, F.I., Laing, R., Bjeirmi, B., & Leon, M., (2022). Examining the causes and impacts of pipeline disasters in Nigeria. *Aims Environmental Science*. (9)5: <https://doi.org/10.3934/environsci.2022037>
- Lee, J., & Kim., D., (2021). Analysis of the Discriminatory Perceptions of Victims on Damage from Environmental Pollution: A Case Study of the Hebei Spirit Oil Spill in South Korea. *Land* 2021, 10(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10101089>
- NEITI (2013). Annual Report of the Nigerian Extractive Industry Transparency Initiative, NEITI, Nigeria. <https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/attachments/2013>.
- Njoku A.O (2016) Effects on the Oil Pipelines Vandalism and its Socio-Economic Development in Nigerian Society. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic Research Vol. 4*, No. 4.
- Nnadih, O.S., & Offiong E. O., (2017). Mitigation of Oil Pipeline Vandalism using small satellite and earth system. *American Journal of Engineering research*. 6(9).
- Nwoke, R.M., James, S.T., & Agbo, O.W., (2022). Oil pipeline vandalisation and its socio-legal effects in Nigeria. *International Journal of Law* 8(6).

- Odalonu, H.B., (2015). Upsurge of oil theft and illegal bunkering in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria: Is there a way out? *Mediterranean Journal of social sciences*, 6(3).
- Okoli, A.C., & Orinya, S., (2013). Oil Pipeline Vandalism and Nigeria's National Security" *Global Journal of Human Social Science*, 13 (5):1-10
- Okoli, A., (2013). The political ecology of the Niger Delta crisis and the prospects lasting peace in the Post-Amnesty Period. *Global Journal of Human Social Science* 13 (3).
- Olawuni, P., Olowoporoku, O., & Daramola, O., (2020). Determinants of Residents' Participation in Disaster Risk Management in Lagos Metropolis Nigeria. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Management*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.18485/ijdrm.2020.2.2.1>
- Oluwatuyi, O., & Ileri, O. N., (2013). Petrol tanker disaster, pipeline vandalization and impacts on regional development in Nigeria. *European. Journal of Science and Engineering*, 1(1), 34-41
- Onuoha, F. (2009)" Why the poor pay with their lives: *Oil pipeline vandalisation, fires and human Security in Nigeria, Disaster* 33(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7717.2008.01079.x>
- Ozogu N A & Olabimtan OH, N. C. Chukwurah NC, M. K. Ukpong M K, D. S. & Daniel D S (2023) Effects and Causes of Illegal Crude Oil Bunkering in Nigeria: Case Study Niger Delta. *American Journal of IR 4.0 and Beyond(AJIRB)*. Volume 2 Issue 1. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajirb.v2i1.1450>
- Petroleum Pipeline Regulations Under Section 136 and 191 Petroleum Industry Act (2021). <https://pia.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2022>
- Solomon, V. A., & Madubuike, S. C., (2011). Impact of Environmental Change on Rural Communities: A Case Study of the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. *Journal of Governance and Development*, 7, 37-45.. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358465266_
- Stewart-Koster, B., Olden, J. D., & Johnson, P. T., (2015). Integrating landscape connectivity and habitat suitability to guide offensive and defensive invasive species management. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 52(2), 366-378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12395>